

Humic substances-assisted immobilization of magnetite onto sawdust increases surface area and copper bonding of the sorbent

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Pollution of water bodies with heavy metals due to anthropogenic activities, in particular metallurgical production, is one of the most acute environmental problems. Heavy metals are highly toxic, prone to bioaccumulation and long-term preservation in aquatic ecosystems, which leads to disruption of biogeochemical cycles and degradation of biodiversity. In this regard, the development of efficient and cost-effective sorbents for the remediation of heavy metal pollution remains a pressing issue.

We synthesized magnetite immobilized on sawdust under two conditions: with and without humic substances. The procedure involved mixing Fe(II)/Fe(III) salts with sawdust, precipitating magnetite in ammoniacal medium, and isolating the products by filtration and drying.

We investigated the specific surface area of the humate-containing sorbent and the effect on the ability of sorbents to adsorb copper from natural waters, comparing it with the sorbent obtained without humate and raw sawdust. The sorbents were characterized using various physico-chemical methods. X-ray phase analysis and Mossbauer spectroscopy confirmed the predominance of the magnetite phase in the synthesized materials. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) specific surface area (SSA) was determined from the linear plot in the relative pressure range of 0.05–0.3 P/P₀. The pore size distribution was calculated in the relative pressure range (P/P₀) from 0.1 to 0.99 using the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Surface characteristics and sorption properties of sawdust-based sorbents

Samples	SD	SD-Fe	SD-Fe-HS
BET Surface Area, m ² /g	12.5	5.3	45.7
Cumulative Pore Volume, ml/g	0.013	0.022	0.074
Average Pore Diameter, nm	3.5	12.9	5.8
Maximum equilibrium adsorption capacity, mg/g.	3.8	7.1	7.8

Modification with Fe₃O₄ reduced the surface area of sawdust, but increased the average pore diameter, indicating the formation of larger pores. The addition of humic substances together with Fe₃O₄ markedly enhanced both surface area and pore volume, which directly correlated with the highest sorption capacity (7.8 mg/g) observed for SD-Fe-HS. These results demonstrate the potential of humic-substance–modified magnetic sorbents as an accessible and efficient tool for the removal of heavy metals from contaminated waters contributing to the mitigation of ecological risks associated with industrial pollution.

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